

Policy Brief: Strengthening Land-Based Mitigation Technologies in Indonesia

Indonesia Case Study – LANDMARC Project

1. Introduction

The LANDMARC (Land Use Based Mitigation for Resilient Climate Pathways) project, funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 program, evaluates Land-Based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) for reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions across sectors such as agriculture, forestry, and land use. These technologies focus on enhancing carbon sequestration and reducing emissions, with the aim of scaling solutions from local to global contexts.

Indonesia's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC) aim for a 29% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030, potentially reaching 41% with international support (Mawardi et al., 2023). This aligns with the Long-Term Strategy for Low Carbon and Climate Resilience 2050. Reforestation is expected to play a critical role, potentially reducing forestry emissions by 35%.

2. Case Study: Land-Based Mitigation Technologies in Indonesia

LANDMARC's Indonesia case study examines LMTs relevant to the country's climate goals, including Forest Management, Agroforestry, Peatland Restoration, and Soil Carbon Enhancement. These LMTs address the interactions between agriculture, forestry, and land use—key emission drivers. However, challenges remain:

Forest Management: Large-scale reforestation faces challenges, particularly in remote areas with low seedling survival. Engaging local communities in sustainable management is crucial for long-term success.

Agroforestry: Economic barriers limit adoption, as farmers prioritize short-term gains over long-term benefits like soil fertility. Financial incentives and market access are needed to promote agroforestry.

Peatland Restoration: Progress has been slow, with only 25% of targets met by 2020, due to funding, expertise, and land-use conflicts. Scaling up is essential for climate mitigation, biodiversity protection, and community livelihoods

Soil Carbon Enhancement: Adoption remains limited due to costs and low awareness. Government, NGOs, and research institutions must promote its economic benefits and provide financial support to smallholder farmers.

3. Main Findings

Climate Benefits of LMTs

LMTs offer significant potential to reduce emissions and enhance carbon sequestration in Indonesia's land-use sector, which is currently one of the largest sources of emissions.

- **Forest Management:** The FOLU Net Sink 2030 strategy provides a solid framework, but stronger enforcement of forest protection laws and increased investment in reforestation are necessary for success.
- **Agroforestry:** Agroforestry systems in Indonesia could sequester up to 30 million tons of carbon annually, while also generating additional income for farmers. However, policies must improve financial incentives and market access to support wider adoption
- **Peatland Restoration:** Restoring degraded peatlands could prevent millions of tons of CO₂ emissions. While progress has been made, large-scale rewetting requires more technical and financial support, with continued community engagement essential.

- **Biochar:** Biochar and other soil carbon enhancement techniques hold potential for improving soil health and carbon sequestration. However, adoption is limited by cost barriers and low farmer awareness, requiring more promotion and support.

Barriers to Adoption

Despite the clear benefits, several barriers are slowing the adoption of LMTs in Indonesia:

- **Economic Challenges:** Many smallholder farmers are reluctant to adopt LMTs because the short-term financial benefits are not immediately clear. For example, the upfront costs of agroforestry and biochar can be high, and the returns are often realized over a longer time horizon.
- **Knowledge and Technological Gaps:** The success of LMTs depends on technical knowledge and access to the right tools. Many farmers lack the training and resources needed to implement these technologies effectively.
- **Policy and Institutional Barriers:** While the Indonesian government has set ambitious climate goals, there is often a gap between policy and implementation. More coherent policies, better coordination across government agencies, and increased funding are needed to scale up LMT adoption.

4. Policy Recommendations

1. Strengthen Forest Management and Peatland Restoration Efforts

The government should prioritize the full implementation of the FOLU Net Sink 2030 strategy, particularly by scaling up reforestation efforts in degraded forest areas. Providing financial support for smallholder farmers engaged in forest conservation and increasing enforcement of anti-logging laws will be essential. Moreover, given the critical role of peatlands in reducing emissions, peatland restoration should be a top priority for Indonesia. The government needs to allocate more funding and resources to the BRG to ensure it meets its restoration targets. Engaging local communities in restoration efforts and promoting sustainable livelihoods through wetland farming (paludiculture) can make restoration more successful and socially inclusive.

2. Expand Agroforestry Initiatives

The Ministry of Agriculture should expand its agroforestry incentive programs to include broader financial support and training for smallholder farmers.

3. Scale Up Peatland Restoration

Peatland restoration must be accelerated by increasing financial support for the BRGM and involving more local communities in restoration efforts. Training programs focused on sustainable peatland use, combined with market-based incentives, can help scale up these efforts.

4. Promote Soil Carbon Enhancement

Biochar has immense potential to improve soil health and sequester carbon, but its adoption remains limited. The government should launch educational campaigns and demonstration projects to show farmers the benefits of biochar. Financial support, such as subsidies for biochar production, will also help overcome the cost barrier. Integrating biochar into Indonesia's broader agricultural policies will ensure its benefits are realized on a national scale.

5. Enhance Monitoring and Reporting Systems

Accurate and transparent monitoring of LMT implementation is crucial for measuring progress and ensuring accountability. Indonesia should invest in improving its Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) systems by incorporating satellite remote sensing and on-the-ground data collection. Involving local communities in this process will improve transparency and help align national policies with local needs.

5. Conclusion

Scaling up LMTs in Indonesia is essential for achieving the country's climate goals and addressing the challenges of deforestation, peatland degradation, and unsustainable agricultural practices. By overcoming the economic, technical, and policy barriers of the four solutions, Indonesia can make significant progress towards reducing emissions while improving ecosystem resilience. Thus, Indonesia must provide financial incentives, improve technical support, and strengthen policy frameworks to unlock the full potential of LMTs.